

THE FORMATION OF THE LEGAL FOUNDATIONS OF LAND AND WATER RELATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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The favorable natural and climatic conditions of Central Asia have allowed people in this region to engage in agriculture and animal husbandry since ancient times. The expansion of irrigation systems has also become crucial for the economy of the republic. Protected lands were supplied with water, and new lands were allocated for the development of agriculture.

However, in addition to providing economic benefits, these actions also had negative consequences. As a result, groundwater levels rose, flooding arable lands with salt and swamp, and orchards and vineyards dried up. After Uzbekistan gained independence in 1991, its land and water resources faced significant changes due to various socio-economic factors and ecological problems. With the independence, along with the development of the agricultural sector, which is one of the main branches of the economy, economic reforms were also implemented.

In the process of building a democratic, legal state based on market relations in the Republic of Uzbekistan, special attention was paid to the rational use of land and water resources, as it is crucial for successfully achieving the priority task of improving the standard of living of the population in social, economic, and cultural terms. In implementing reforms in this area, particular emphasis was placed on strengthening specialization in agriculture, developing it at an accelerated pace, and industrializing the sector. Given that these factors are of significant importance, the statement of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, that "The priority task of further reforming agriculture is, first and foremost, the rational use of land and water resources," plays a legally decisive role in regulating land-related issues.

Creating a system of measures to protect land resources and use them rationally, as well as safeguarding the rights and legal interests of landowners, landholders, and land users, and ensuring the rule of law in this area, is one of the key socio-economic and political tasks of society. Indeed, the economic

potential of the state, the material foundation of society, and the well-being of citizens largely depend on addressing such pressing issues as ensuring legality in relation to land, using land in accordance with legal requirements, preventing violations of land legislation, and maintaining law and order in the field of land relations.

In the states 68, Chapter 12, Section 3 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan are shown that: "Land, subsoil resources, water, flora and fauna, and other natural resources are national wealth, and their rational use is essential. They are under state protection. Land may be privately owned based on conditions and procedures stipulated by law, ensuring its rational use and protection as national wealth."

To further improve the field of water usage and protection, and to effectively combat emerging new threats, a number of institutional and regulatory-legal changes are being implemented in the sector. In particular, amendments and additions were made to the Law "On Water and Water Use" through Law No. O'RQ-733, dated November 30, 2021, expanding the Cabinet of Ministers' authority in regulating water relations. Additionally, the Cabinet of Ministers was granted the authority to implement measures aimed at developing water management, ensuring the rational and efficient use of water, mitigating the negative impacts of water scarcity, approving other programs related to water and water use, and endorsing procedures for state support in introducing water-saving technologies.

Furthermore, a number of important decrees and resolutions related to the sector have been adopted, including the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 2, 2018, titled "Measures to Improve the Efficiency of Water Resource Usage," the Resolution of July 10, 2020, "On Approval of the Concept for the Development of Water Management in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030," and the Presidential Decree of June 23, 2023, "Measures to Effectively Organize State Management in the Water Sector Within the Framework of Administrative Reforms."

As a result, comprehensive measures are being implemented in the country to ensure the rational management of surface water bodies, adherence to the rules of water use and consumption, as well as identifying violations in the water management sector and addressing the causes and conditions leading to such violations.

In particular, great attention is being paid to the agricultural sector in the context of modern Uzbekistan, with specific measures being implemented to stimulate the production of agricultural products.

The "Uzbekistan – 2030" strategy also highlights measures aimed at sharply increasing productivity and profitability in agriculture as a key task. In this regard, it is important to note that, under the initiative of the President, systematic reforms are being carried out in the agricultural sector, and the legal foundations of the sector are being improved, resulting in the formation of a favorable agro-business environment in the country. The burdens on farmers have been alleviated, and new jobs have been created. For example, by reducing the area of cotton and grain fields by 200,000 hectares and offering them to our citizens based on a competitive process, over 2 million permanent and seasonal jobs have been created.

In conclusion, it is important to emphasize that Uzbekistan is developing a comprehensive legal framework aimed at the sustainable management of these critical resources, adapting to the emerging challenges related to land and water relations. Despite facing serious issues related to land and water resources due to agricultural needs, urbanization, and the impact of climate change, the legislative framework continues to function actively to address these challenges.

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